

Article

Fostering Inclusion: A Virtual Reality Experience to Raise Awareness of Dyslexia-Related Barriers in University Settings

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Abstract: This work introduces the design, implementation, and validation of a virtual reality (VR) experience aimed at promoting the inclusion of individuals with dyslexia in university settings. Unlike traditional awareness methods, this immersive approach offers a novel way to foster empathy by allowing participants to experience firsthand the challenges faced by students with dyslexia. Specifically, the experience raises awareness by exposing non-dyslexic individuals to the difficulties commonly encountered by dyslexic students. In the virtual environment, participants explore a virtual campus with multiple buildings, navigating between them while completing tasks and simultaneously encountering barriers that simulate some of the challenges faced by individuals with dyslexia. These barriers include reading signs with shifting letters, following directional arrows that may point incorrectly, and dealing with a lack of assistance. The campus is a comprehensive model featuring both indoor and outdoor spaces and supporting various modes of locomotion. To validate the experience, more than 30 non-dyslexic participants from the university environment, mainly professors and students, evaluated it through ad hoc satisfaction surveys. The results indicated heightened awareness of the barriers encountered by students with dyslexia, with participants deeming the experience a valuable tool for increasing visibility and fostering understanding of dyslexic students.

Keywords: virtual reality; inclusivity; barrier simulation; educational technology; dyslexia; specific learning disorders; awareness; serious games

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1. Introduction

Digital integration into education is gradually transforming the understanding and support of learning differences, showing more and more promising results. Among these technologies, VR and augmented reality (AR) allow the creation of immersive environments where users can experience and engage with simulated real-world obstacles [1]. In particular, VR technologies are increasingly included in diverse segments of society, increasing awareness of social issues. Despite its potential, research into leveraging VR for comprehension regarding learning disorders, such as dyslexia, remains in its early stages, especially in higher education settings [2,3].

Among the diverse learning disorders, dyslexia is one of the most prevalent learning disorders, yet it often goes undiagnosed in its early stages. Dyslexia is a neurobiologically

specific learning disorder (SLD) that affects cognitive and social development [4,5]. Typically neurodevelopmental and often genetic, it impairs reading and language processing and is frequently accompanied by challenges in orientation, comprehension, and time management within academic settings [6,7]. These barriers can profoundly impact the educational experiences of affected students, highlighting the need for innovative approaches to foster awareness and inclusion. It is estimated that dyslexia affects between 5% and 10% of the global population [8]. However, more recent studies suggest that this figure is likely underreported, with the actual prevalence potentially ranging between 15% and 20% [9]. Moreover, these statistics must account for previously noted diagnostic variability, which opposes establishing a standardized and precise measurement framework [10].

While prior studies have explored VR [11] and also AR [12] applications in education, few have focused on its potential to portray the lived experiences of individuals with SLDs. To effectively support students with dyslexia, it is essential to understand the hurdles in their daily lives, especially in the learning environment. This approach would allow classmates and teachers to directly understand the importance of offering support to help students overcome the barriers they encounter [13]. Existing research in this field underscores the importance of this understanding in creating supportive learning environments. For instance, earlier works have demonstrated how VR can effectively simulate sensory or physical impairments, but there is limited evidence of its application for cognitive and learning challenges [14]. Other studies have explored the role of VR in childhood education for students with dyslexia, demonstrating its potential to enhance cognitive skills and reading abilities [15–17]. However, research on the application of immersive simulations in higher education remains scarce, particularly in addressing how such experiences can shape perceptions and foster inclusive learning environments for students with dyslexia. This gap in research provides an opportunity to explore how immersive simulations might influence perceptions of and attitudes toward students with dyslexia, increasing awareness and enabling inclusive education.

The purpose of this study is to design, implement, and validate a VR experience that immerses participants in the role of a university student with dyslexia. Within this virtual campus, participants navigate various campus buildings to complete tasks, encountering barriers that reflect the challenges associated with this SLD. Guidance is provided through a map, directional arrows, and signs. Through this approach, the study aims to increase consciousness of the specific barriers students with dyslexia face and to promote awareness among non-dyslexic individuals. Key features of the experience include tasks such as interpreting shifting text on signs, navigating misleading directional arrows, and managing high-pressure situations without help. All of these scenarios mirror real-world barriers faced by individuals with dyslexia [6]. This work fosters the potential to enhance educational practices and increase VR's role in promoting inclusion. By involving non-dyslexic university participants in the experience, including students and professors, the study provides valuable insights into how simulated experiences can reshape perceptions, and it allows for a deeper understanding of dyslexia at the higher education level. Beyond raising awareness, this initiative aims to foster the adoption of more inclusive educational strategies and improve the availability of compensatory tools for students with dyslexia. By promoting a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by these students, the study encourages institutions to implement supportive policies and accommodations that enhance academic engagement, attendance, and overall attainment. Moreover, as part of the VRAllexia project, the outcomes of this work contribute to a broader framework for institutional change, including the release of a Memorandum of Understanding (<https://vrailexia.eu/the-project/io5-outside-the-box/>, accessed on 17 February 2025),

which provides concrete guidelines for fostering inclusion and improving accessibility in higher education settings.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related works, providing a comprehensive overview of existing research on integrating VR in education and its potential to simulate the experiences of individuals with SLDs, with a particular focus on dyslexia. Section 3 outlines the VR application, describing the design, development, and implementation of the VR experience, as well as the methodologies employed to assess its effectiveness in promoting awareness. Section 4 presents the results, highlighting key findings from participant interactions with the VR experience, including changes in the perception and understanding of dyslexia. Finally, Section 5 concludes the work by discussing the broader implications of the study, its limitations, and opportunities for future research in both educational practices and VR-based inclusion initiatives.

2. Related Works

This section reviews the literature on the use of VR for raising awareness and simulating barriers, particularly in the context of dyslexia. It examines recent studies and experiences, highlighting their results and exploring the potential of VR as a tool for fostering understanding among individuals without dyslexia in university settings.

VR has emerged as a powerful tool in promoting inclusion by providing immersive experiences that foster empathy for and understanding of individuals with disabilities [18]. VR allows users to experience the world from the perspective of individuals with physical or cognitive impairments, facilitating emotional and cognitive connections that can lead to greater social awareness and compassion. For instance, VR has been employed in workshops on social inclusion, helping participants better comprehend the challenges faced by others [19]. A notable example of a direct impact in this field is Meta's "VR for Good" program [20], which encompasses multiple virtual reality experiences designed to enhance awareness of various marginalized communities. Moreover, VR can be used to create inclusive environments that reproduce the specific needs of individuals with disabilities. For example, VR can simulate scenarios that replicate real-world challenges faced by people with autism, helping both individuals and society at large gain a better understanding of the condition [21]. Other studies also prove that VR can help people with the training and rehabilitation of people with hearing impairments and intellectual disabilities, teaching them to interact with their surroundings in new and beneficial ways, such as using visual or tactile cues in place of audio [22].

The application of VR to simulate the experience of physical or cognitive barriers has proven to be a valuable tool for raising awareness about people with disabilities. One of the most prominent uses of VR in this context is in the simulation of sensory impairments, such as blindness, hearing loss, or cognitive disabilities, to help participants understand the challenges faced by individuals with these conditions. For example, the VR experience "Notes on Blindness: Into Darkness" [23] immerses users in the experience of gradually losing their vision, using audio tracks to represent how a person with blindness perceives their environment. Similarly, studies have shown that VR simulations of the obstacles faced by wheelchair users can be effective in changing participants' attitudes toward disability and fostering a sense of empathy [24]. These VR experiences have the power to evoke a sense of perspective that might be difficult to achieve through traditional awareness-raising methods, creating lasting emotional and cognitive connections between users and those living with these challenges. Moreover, VR has been used to simulate disorientation and cognitive overload, which can mirror the challenges faced by individuals with SLDs such as dyslexia. These simulations allow participants to experience firsthand how difficult it

can be to navigate complex environments, read text, or manage multitasking under stress, thus promoting empathy and understanding [13].

Focusing on the field of dyslexia, VR has also been utilized in various studies to support dyslexic children by providing engaging, interactive environments that address their specific learning needs. For example, the European project FORDYSVAR has developed a VR game designed for dyslexic children aged 10–16 to help them improve their reading and language skills in a more interactive and enjoyable way [25]. Other studies have explored how VR can help children with dyslexia overcome challenges related to attention, memory, and task-switching by offering immersive and focused learning environments that are both fun and educational [26]. Similarly, [27] highlights the increasing adoption of VR in education, reporting promising results from a large-scale study involving more than 2000 teachers.

Although these studies primarily focus on assisting individuals with dyslexia by providing adaptive learning and support mechanisms, our study is inspired by their underlying goal: improving the quality of life and educational experiences of dyslexic individuals. Rather than targeting dyslexic students themselves, our approach leverages VR to raise awareness among non-dyslexic individuals, helping them understand the cognitive barriers associated with dyslexia. This aligns with the broader objective shared by the aforementioned projects, fostering inclusivity by bridging the gap between those who experience these challenges and those who interact with them in academic and social environments.

Finally, in the context of higher education, VR is beginning to be applied to support adult students with dyslexia. The VRAllexia project is one of the first initiatives designed to assist university students with dyslexia by leveraging VR and artificial intelligence technologies [2]. This project aims to develop customized learning support tools using VR simulations that replicate the cognitive challenges faced by dyslexic students in a university setting, such as difficulties with reading, note-taking, and navigating among large educational buildings. In addition to its VR simulations, the VRAllexia project implements different recommendation systems to provide tailored educational interventions, ensuring that the support is personalized to the individual's needs [28]. This innovative approach provides valuable insights into how VR can be used as a genuine assistive technology that can help students with dyslexia succeed in higher education [29]. VRAllexia similarly uses VR to administer psychometric tests without the need for expert presence, making it easier to detect conditions in individuals who might otherwise remain undiagnosed in adulthood [30].

3. VR Empathy Experience

During this section, the proposed experience and its implementation will be detailed. This includes an overview of the tools used for development, the workflow followed throughout the process, the main elements involved, the simulation of barriers, and, finally, the gameplay design and the available experience.

The experience implementation was performed using the Unity game engine [31] for deployment on Meta Quest devices [32]. The software development followed the Scrum methodology and adhered to best practices, resulting in an iterative process [33]. This approach led to multiple versions of the virtual environment's scenarios, ensuring their quality and functionality, and the effectiveness of tasks performed at various campus locations was thoroughly validated.

3.1. Overview

This section provides an overview of the methodology followed in this work. The proposed experience in this work consists of performing a series of tasks in a virtual environment that simulates a university campus. This campus is vast and consists of numerous similar buildings, which will complicate navigation through the map. The goal of the experience is to simulate some of the barriers faced by university students with dyslexia in their daily lives. The design guidelines followed for the development of this environment are defined below.

At the beginning of the experience, participants find themselves outside a university campus in front of a sign that shows them how to take their first steps within the virtual environment. Following the provided instructions, the user will go through a brief tutorial on the various available modes of locomotion, which will be very important for navigating the entire campus. After this, the participant must locate a map that will give them a series of directions to ensure that they can reach the exam room on time.

To reach their destination, they will need to complete two tasks: collecting the materials needed for the exam and finding the classroom where the exam is being held. However, during these tasks, participants will face significant barriers similar to those that students with dyslexia encounter in their daily lives, such as difficulties with reading, challenges in orientation, and issues with memorization. These barriers will be simulated within the experience using different strategies, such as altering the order of letters in words and providing hard-to-interpret maps, among others, which are detailed further in Section 3.4.

If the user successfully completes the tasks on time, they will reach the exam room and fulfill their objective on the campus.

In addition, the objective of the virtual campus is not only to raise awareness about dyslexia in university environments but also to serve as a link between other VR experiences that aim to address more specific aspects of dyslexia awareness and other vulnerable groups. These experiences will be incorporated into the campus as they are developed, ultimately aiming to create a comprehensive virtual environment that allows users to understand firsthand the challenges these groups face.

Once the experience is completed, its effectiveness will be evaluated through a survey. The questions were designed based on recommendation models tailored to support dyslexic students [34], integrating elements from the VR aspect of the experience. This evaluation will serve as an initial analysis of the experience's effectiveness, preparing the way for future implementations and the integration of empathy tests into the campus environment. A more detailed analysis will then assess their impact on raising awareness about dyslexia and fostering empathy.

3.2. Design

The virtual environment simulates a large-scale university campus composed of multiple interconnected buildings and pathways. This environment includes seven distinct buildings that participants must navigate as they complete the tasks outlined in the experience. The design prioritizes inclusivity and immersion, leveraging VR to simulate real-world challenges faced by individuals with dyslexia.

To raise awareness of dyslexia and highlight the contributions of individuals with this SLD, each building within the campus is named after renowned figures with dyslexia. This approach aims to help non-dyslexic users recognize the achievements of individuals who have successfully overcome similar challenges, fostering a deeper connection between the experience and real-world examples of resilience and success. In addition, to enhance the sense of presence and realism, the environment incorporates ambient sounds and common visual elements found in real university settings, such as trees, benches, bike

parkings, and avatars representing students. These elements collectively enrich the immersive experience while emphasizing empathy for the barriers encountered by individuals with dyslexia.

Among the virtual campus's core components, the following elements stand out due to their significance in promoting navigation, task progression, and overall engagement:

- **Maps:** To facilitate navigation within the expansive campus, two types of maps are provided to participants:
 - **Vertical Map:** this simplified map highlights only the user's current location and the target destination, enabling a focused and streamlined experience (see Figure 1a).
 - **Interactive 3D Map:** Offering a comprehensive, overhead 3D view of the campus, this map displays the names and positions of all buildings along with the user's location. Users can interact with this map to receive real-time navigation assistance toward specific destinations by pressing a designated button (see Figure 1b).

(a) Vertical Map.

(b) Interactive 3D Map.

Figure 1. Maps.

- **Students:** The campus environment features diverse avatars representing students engaged in common activities, such as group interactions or solitary walks (see Figure 2a). These non-playable characters (NPCs) add vibrancy and realism to the experience, simulating the bustling nature of a real university setting. However, participants cannot interact with these avatars, nor will the NPCs provide guidance or assistance, further reinforcing the sense of independence and potential disorientation.
- **Signals:** Informative signage is strategically placed throughout the campus to guide participants in completing challenges and navigating to key locations (see Figure 2b). Initially, these signs provide clear instructions (tutorial); however, as the experience progresses, some signs become increasingly difficult to read, simulating the textual decoding challenges often experienced by individuals with dyslexia. In addition to directional signs, another set of signs identifies the entrances to campus buildings, displaying their respective names to assist with orientation. Some signs are dynamically modified based on the user's behavior. For example, the signs at the building entrances will indicate, when a participant attempts to enter the wrong building for the current task, that they are not in the correct building. This dynamic feature helps guide the user and reinforces the navigation challenges inherent to the experience. This dual purpose, navigation and simulation, underscores the barriers associated with reading and spatial awareness.

- **Beacon:** In order to facilitate task progression and reduce uncertainty, a visual beacon system is employed to highlight critical points within the campus. The beacon appears as a circle of light projected onto the ground, signaling locations such as building entrances, exits, and other significant waypoints (see Figure 2c). At any given time, the active beacon guides participants sequentially through key stages of the experience. Additionally, there is a challenge beacon, observable from anywhere on the campus, that provides a clear indicator of the active 3D map corresponding to the current challenge. This helps users stay oriented and focused on the specific task at hand. The structured approach of the beacon system aids participants in navigating simulated barriers and completing tasks more effectively.

Figure 2. Different elements included in the virtual campus.

3.3. Interaction

Within the virtual environment, users can engage in various types of interactions, each designed to enhance immersion and provide different ways of navigating and manipulating the virtual space. The experience is implemented in 6 Degrees of Freedom (6DoF), allowing users to move freely along all three translational axes (forward/backward, up/down, left/right), as well as rotate along all three rotational axes (pitch, yaw, and roll). This degree of freedom contributes significantly to a more immersive and realistic experience [35]. The interactions are facilitated through the use of controllers, which are essential for completing tasks and experiencing the environment fully. The primary interaction types are as follows:

- **Continuous locomotion:** This interaction simulates continuous movement through the virtual environment, allowing users to move freely along the three translational axes and rotate as they explore the space. Continuous locomotion offers precise and uninterrupted navigation, providing a high level of immersion. However, it can induce motion sickness due to the sensory mismatch between visual input and the vestibular system, and in room-scale setups, it is limited by the physical space available. See Figure 3a.
- **Teleportation:** Also known as parabolic locomotion, this interaction enables users to instantly jump to a selected point in the virtual environment. By pointing at a destination, users are teleported through a parabolic arc, overcoming the physical space constraints. Teleportation provides an alternative to continuous locomotion, making it especially useful for large virtual environments. While it reduces motion sickness, it can disrupt immersion and hinder the creation of a mental map of the environment. However, this issue is minimized in open spaces like the campus, where the layout and open areas reduce the need for frequent teleportation and help maintain spatial orientation. See Figure 3b.

- **Button press:** This interaction allows users to activate virtual buttons by bringing the controller close to the corresponding button in the environment, similar to physically pressing a button. This action involves rotational DoF (via wrist or arm movement), but it may also require some translational movement to position the controller accurately. Button pressing is typically used for interacting with 3D map buttons or virtual controls, offering a simple and effective way to engage with the environment.
- **Grab/release objects:** This interaction enables users to pick up objects within the virtual environment by positioning the controllers over them and pressing the grab button. Both translational and rotational DoF are required to manipulate objects effectively. Releasing an object is accomplished by simply releasing the corresponding button. This method is integral to tasks involving the handling and transportation of objects, enhancing the realism and tactile quality of the virtual experience.

Figure 3. Locomotion modes using the controllers. (a) Continuous locomotion. (b) Teleportation.

These four interaction types, facilitated by 6 DoF, constitute the foundation of user engagement within the virtual environment. The integration of translational and rotational movements, combined with diverse interaction modalities, results in a highly immersive and adaptable experience, thereby enhancing user presence and engagement in the simulated environment.

3.4. Simulating Barriers for Dyslexics

The main objective of the experience is to raise participants' awareness of the barriers encountered by students with dyslexia during their higher education years. To achieve this, a series of simulated barriers have been designed and integrated into the virtual environment to reflect similar challenges. It is important to emphasize that these barriers are not intended to replicate dyslexia itself but to mimic the difficulties it can cause, such as slower reading, disorientation, and feelings of isolation or lack of support.

One of the primary challenges associated with dyslexia is difficulty in reading and comprehending text. To simulate this challenge, two distinct strategies have been employed: letter movement and word substitution.

- **Letter movement:** This barrier involves dynamically and randomly rearranging the letters, except for the first letter of the word, within individual words, as illustrated in Figure 4a. In this example, the letters of the word "exam" change their order, forming nonexistent words like "exma". This effect is applied to the full text of informative signs that describe tasks on the campus and also in the names of the buildings that are reflected in the maps, making the text harder to read and increasing the time needed for comprehension.
- **Word swapping:** This barrier involves replacing some words in the text with other existing words that have similar sounds, which is one of the primary issues associ-

ated with surface dyslexia [36]. In this way, during the experience, words in task instructions are continuously swapped, forcing the user to pause and consider what the actual instructions are. This is illustrated in Figure 4b, where the word “stairs” is replaced with “stare”.

Figure 4. Simulation of reading difficulties. (a) Letter movement. (b) Word swapping.

Another significant challenge faced by university students with dyslexia is orientation within large environments [37]. These environments are often vast, with similar-looking buildings and limited signage to guide navigation between locations. To replicate this challenge, the virtual campus was designed as a large-scale map featuring similar paths and structures. The scaled dimensions of the buildings and streets within the modeled campus are depicted in Figure 5a. Furthermore, the 3D maps represent the shapes of buildings in a manner that does not fully correspond to their actual structures within the virtual environment. Similarly, vertical maps omit the names of the main buildings, further complicating navigation. This design compels users to rely on both types of maps to orient themselves effectively and reach their destination.

Additionally, a help button was incorporated into the 3D maps, enabling participants to display guiding arrows on the ground, as illustrated in Figure 5b, to assist them in navigating to their destination. However, to ensure that this feature does not entirely mitigate the orientation challenge, the arrows are deliberately designed to point in the wrong direction 25% of the time, introducing an additional layer of disorientation. This design emulates some of the barriers encountered by individuals with dyslexia, particularly difficulties with left-right or up-down orientation. By occasionally providing incorrect directions, this feature simulates the disorientation and navigational challenges that individuals with dyslexia may face in spatial environments.

Another significant barrier faced by students with dyslexia is the lack of support from peers and teachers [13]. This sense of isolation and frustration often exacerbates the difficulties of their academic journey and can, in some cases, result in the abandonment of their studies. To replicate this experience, participants are placed in a campus environment populated with NPCs representing students and peers, but interaction with them for assistance is not permitted. Furthermore, the support provided through the virtual experience itself is intentionally limited and, at times, deliberately misleading. This design choice seeks to heighten the user’s sense of frustration, transforming seemingly straightforward tasks into complex challenges and effectively simulating the emotional and practical difficulties experienced by students with dyslexia.

Figure 5. Simulation of orientation barriers. (a) Scaled dimension of the virtual campus. (b) Help option providing right and wrong directions.

3.5. Gameplay

The experience is designed to span multiple locations across the campus and is structured into distinct stages or levels. This section provides a detailed analysis of each phase of the experience, including the specific tasks participants are required to complete at each stage.

Figure 6 illustrates the layout of these levels, mapping the progression from the user's entry into the virtual environment to the conclusion of the experience. Each stage, along with the corresponding tasks, is classified into three main categories, which are outlined below:

- **Start–End Stages:** These stages mark the beginning and conclusion of the experience. They include the introductory tutorial at the start and the final exam, where the experience comes to an end.
- **Main Building Task:** These stages involve specific challenges within certain campus buildings, where participants face dyslexia-related barriers, particularly those related to reading and text comprehension.
- **Navigation Stage:** These stages require participants to locate specific points on the campus to progress to the next phase. While the start and end points of these stages are predefined, as shown in Figure 6, the path taken by the player is not fixed and is influenced by the user's navigation choices.

The user progresses through a series of stages, each designed to represent a distinct type of interaction and challenge within the virtual campus. The following breakdown categorizes the levels by their specific tasks and explains their relationship to the previously described phase types: Start–End Stages, Main Building Tasks, and Navigation Stages.

1. **Tutorial Stage (Start–End Stage):** The experience begins with a tutorial stage located at the campus entrance. The primary objective of this stage is to familiarize users with the controls and basic navigation mechanics of the virtual environment. Informative signs provide guidance on operating the controllers and selecting between different locomotion options to navigate to the first 3D interactive map. Upon reaching the map, users receive instructions on interacting with elements such as virtual buttons. Successfully pressing the button transitions the experience into the next phase, marking the formal commencement of the user's task-based journey.
2. **Journey 1 (Navigation Stage):** Following the tutorial, the user encounters their first navigation challenge. A sign displaying instructions directs them to their next destination, utilizing the "Letters Movement" barrier to simulate the difficulties individuals

with dyslexia may experience when interpreting text (see Section 3.4). The instructions indicate that the user must proceed to the Agatha Christie building to collect materials required for an exam. This navigation task requires the user to interpret signs displaying building names and follow them to reach the designated location, thereby testing their ability to navigate the campus under conditions analogous to those faced by individuals with dyslexia.

3. **Agatha Christie (Main Building Task):** Upon entering the Agatha Christie building, the user encounters another barrier: a sign displaying text altered by the “Letters Movement” effect. The task requires the user to locate a notebook and pen within the building, collect them, and place them in their virtual backpack before proceeding to the exam room. Upon completing this task, the user is informed that the exam room is located in the Galileo Galilei building. This challenge not only simulates the difficulties associated with reading impairments but also underscores the importance of time management, as the user must complete the task within a limited time frame.
4. **Journey 2 (Navigation Stage):** After exiting the Agatha Christie building, the user must navigate to the Galileo Galilei building using the newly provided instructions. This stage introduces a new 3D map to assist the user in locating the building. The map includes an interactive help function, which offers additional guidance when required. The user is tasked with traversing the campus to reach the Galileo Galilei building, marking a key milestone in this phase of the experience.

Figure 6. (a) Campus render indicating the locations of the main stages of the experience. (b) Flow of experience stages. (c) Legend representing the different types of levels.

5. **Galileo Galilei (Main Building Task):** Upon entering the Galileo Galilei building, the user encounters a room featuring a staircase, a countdown timer, and two hallways. A new sign appears, utilizing the “Swapping Words” barrier to simulate another challenge faced by individuals with dyslexia—difficulty with word recognition. This sign provides instructions specifying the floor and hallway the user must follow to locate the exam room. The countdown timer introduces a time-sensitive element, replicating the stress and pressure that students may experience during exams.
6. **Exam Classroom (Start–End Stage):** Finally, the user reaches the exam room, where they receive instructions to begin the exam. These instructions, while seemingly

straightforward, contain “swapped” words that resemble real words but are, in fact, nonsensical (e.g., “Go to your zona” instead of “Go to your zone”). This final task simulates the challenges of reading comprehension and word recognition challenges commonly experienced by individuals with dyslexia in academic settings. Upon completing this task, the experience concludes.

An example of the gameplay is available on the YouTube platform (<https://youtu.be/j0hBD1j5bgc>, accessed on 17 February 2025). The complete experience is available as a free download via SideQuest (<https://sidequestvr.com/app/37775>, accessed on 17 February 2025).

4. Evaluation of the Experience

This section details the methodological framework used to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed VR experience in fostering empathy and raising awareness about dyslexia. The assessment is structured into three key aspects: the features of the participants involved in the study, the methods employed for data collection and analysis, and the instruments used to measure the impact of the experience.

4.1. Participants

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed method as a VR experience aimed at raising awareness about dyslexia, an initial evaluation was conducted with 32 participants from the higher education sector. These participants were selected from volunteers who expressed interest in the experience during a project’s dissemination campaign carried out at the University of Córdoba (Spain). Socio-demographic data were collected during the participant selection process to analyze the methodology’s applicability across different demographic groups, with a primary focus on gender, age, and participants’ academic or professional roles within the higher education context. Table 1 contains information on these characteristics for the 32 participants selected for this study. During the selection process, efforts were made to maintain a balance in the gender of participants, ultimately resulting in a slightly higher participation of male participants, comprising approximately 59% of the total sample. Regarding profiles, the majority of the experience was conducted with university students who shared classes with dyslexic students, representing the largest group (53.17%). Nonetheless, a significant number of teachers of students with dyslexia also showed interest in the experience (21.88%), as well as other individuals who, despite not being educationally connected to someone with dyslexia, had a relative with dyslexia. Concerning age, as previously mentioned, the tool was primarily used by students, making the predominant age range between 18 and 26 years, with over 60% of participants falling within this range.

Table 1. Socio-demographic features of the participants in the study.

Feature	Subgroup	#	Percentage
Gender	Female	13	59.38
	Male	19	40.62
	Other	0	0.00
Age	[18, 26)	20	62.5
	[26, 50]	10	31.25
	>50	2	6.25
Participant profile	Dyslexic relative	6	18.75
	Higher education student	17	53.12
	Higher education professor	7	21.88
	None	2	6.25

4.2. Methods

The evaluation was conducted through a controlled study with a structured data collection process, ensuring the validity and reliability of the findings. The primary aim was to determine how the VR experience influences users’ understanding of dyslexia-related challenges. In order to do that a selected group of participants engaged in the VR experience under supervised conditions, after which they were asked to complete a structured questionnaire that will be defined later.

The theoretical framework guiding the immersive learning experience is based on constructivist and experiential learning theories. Constructivist and experiential learning theories emphasize active, learner-centered engagement, where participants acquire knowledge through meaningful interactions with their environment. In this context, the VR experience was designed to provide an immersive simulation that exposes users to the barriers faced by dyslexic individuals, encouraging a deeper understanding through direct experience and reflection [38]. Additionally, the cognitive theory of multimedia learning informed the integration of visual and interactive elements to enhance engagement and retention. By simulating real-world scenarios and embedding dyslexia-related challenges, the experience aligns with these pedagogical principles, ensuring that learners actively engage with the presented difficulties, rather than passively receiving information.

All participants provided informed consent before engaging in the study, ensuring they were fully aware of the research objectives and the handling of their data. The study complied with all ethical guidelines, including Organic Law 3/2018 on Personal Data Protection and the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki [39,40]. Ethical approval for the study was granted by the institutional ethics committee (approval number 367). In addition, to ensure data privacy, all information obtained was treated with strict confidentiality. The questionnaire was designed to be anonymous, including an introductory section explaining the study’s objectives, followed by an informed consent form.

4.3. Instruments

To evaluate the quality of the experience and its effectiveness as a tool for raising awareness about dyslexia, a questionnaire-based evaluation methodology was developed. The questionnaire consists of 15 questions to be completed after participating in the experience, divided into three categories: socio-demographic data, VR experience quality, and dyslexia awareness. The design of the questions was informed by recommendation models aimed at supporting dyslexic students [34] combined with the VR dimension of the experience. Finally, a general evaluation question regarding the overall experience is also included. Table 2 presents the list of questions organized by category. All items are answered using a 5-point Likert scale except for socio-demographic questions.

The collected data provided quantitative insights into how users perceived the VR experience and whether it effectively enhanced their understanding of dyslexia-related challenges. The next section presents and discusses the results obtained from the evaluation.

Table 2. Survey questions divided by categories.

Category	Question
Socio-demographic information	Gender
	Age
	Relationship to a dyslexic student *
VR experience quality	VR prior experience
	Motion sickness
	Visual immersion
	Interaction within the environment

Table 2. Cont.

Category	Question
Barrier simulation	Navigation among buildings Finding the exam class Use of the help option
Dyslexia awareness	Awareness of dyslexia Experience with empathy applications Effectiveness of the virtual campus in promoting dyslexia awareness
Overall	Overall rating of the experience

* The following types of relationships with a dyslexic student were considered: (1) classmate (2) teacher (3) relative (4) other (5) none.

5. Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the results of the study, focusing on the effectiveness of the empathy experience both as a VR application and as a tool for raising awareness about dyslexia. The results are structured into two main aspects: the assessment of the VR application in terms of usability and immersion, and the evaluation of its effectiveness in simulating barriers and raising awareness about dyslexia.

5.1. VR Application

In order to assess the quality of the proposed tool, it is critical to evaluate not only its effectiveness in achieving its primary objective, raising awareness about dyslexia, but also its ability to effectively utilize the unique features of VR. Therefore, the first evaluation aspect focused on assessing the quality of the VR experience in terms of immersion, interaction, and user comfort. Figure 7 illustrates the responses to four key questions regarding prior VR experience, motion sickness, visual immersion, and interaction within the virtual environment.

Figure 7. Responses to the questions measuring the quality of the VR application. (a) Have you ever tried VR before the experience? (b) Did you experience nausea, loss of balance, or discomfort during the experience? (c) How much did the visual aspects of the environment engage you? (d) How compelling was your sense of moving around and interacting within the virtual environment?

The questionnaire results revealed that a significant proportion of participants had no prior experience with VR, making this their first encounter with a complete setup

involving a headset and controllers. Conversely, 28% of participants reported familiarity with VR equipment, providing valuable feedback based on their previous exposure to other VR applications or games. Regarding discomfort or motion sickness, the findings were predominantly positive. The majority of participants reported no sickness, with only one individual experiencing moderate symptoms and none reporting severe discomfort. In terms of immersion, participants generally expressed favorable opinions. Specifically, 44% indicated feeling “Very immersed”, and 16% reported being “Totally immersed” in the virtual environment. Among the remaining participants, the most commonly cited issue was that the use of controllers for locomotion, particularly teleportation, diminished their sense of immersion. Finally, most participants expressed high satisfaction with the interaction mechanics and locomotion options within the virtual environment. However, the primary criticism is centered on the limited physical space available, which restricted freer physical movement.

5.2. Barrier Simulation and Dyslexia Awareness

The objective of this study is to raise awareness about the challenges faced by dyslexic students in higher education. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed tool in achieving this goal, the evaluation questions were divided into two categories: the simulation of barriers and awareness of dyslexia. The first category focused on assessing the extent to which the simulated barriers hinder task completion during the VR experience. The second category aimed to evaluate participants’ prior knowledge of dyslexia as an SLD and how their perceptions of dyslexic students are influenced after participating in the experience.

Regarding the barriers, Figure 8 illustrates the responses obtained when participants were asked about the difficulties encountered while performing the two main tasks of the experience.

Figure 8. Responses to the questions measuring the effectiveness of the application in simulating barriers. (a) How challenging did you find navigating among the buildings? (b) How challenging did you find locating the classroom for the exam?

The first task required participants to navigate between various campus buildings (see Figure 8a). During this task, participants encountered barriers related to orientation within a monotonous and large-scale environment, as well as difficulties in reading the instructions on signs due to the implemented “Letter movement” strategy. To address these challenges, the experience included mitigation measures, such as the availability of various maps and a help option that displayed guiding arrows on the ground to guide participants between buildings. Despite these aids, only 12 out of 32 participants utilized the help function, as most preferred to complete the task without additional assistance. Participants generally identified this task as the most challenging, citing their main difficulty as transferring the information from the provided maps, particularly the 3D interactive maps, to the virtual campus space.

The second task involved finding the exam classroom within the building where the final exam takes place (see Figure 8b). Upon entering the building, participants are presented with confusing instructions generated using the “Word swapping” strategy.

This challenge is further intensified by the monotonous design of the building's floors, which makes it difficult for participants to easily distinguish between them. Despite these barriers, participants generally found this task to be straightforward, noting that the allotted time was more than sufficient. While some participants needed to review the instructions multiple times to fully understand them, the overall simplicity and limited number of steps contributed to the task being perceived as easy.

On the other hand, the responses to the questions regarding the awareness of dyslexia are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Responses to the questions about participants' dyslexia awareness. (a) How would you rate your understanding of dyslexia? (b) How useful do you consider the VR experience in raising awareness about dyslexia?

The first notable finding is the general lack of knowledge about dyslexia, with more than 60% of participants either being unaware of what this learning disorder is or having only heard about it (see Figure 9a). In contrast, more than 90% of participants indicated that the campus experience is "Very useful" or "Extremely useful" in raising awareness about dyslexia (see Figure 9b). Participants frequently noted that they had not previously considered how the challenges associated with this learning disorder could result in significant difficulties when performing seemingly simple tasks. Only one participant reported finding the tool not useful for raising awareness about dyslexia. This individual stated that he did not fully understand the connection between the tasks and challenges presented during the experience or the definition of dyslexia difficulties.

5.3. Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the potential of VR as an effective tool for raising awareness about dyslexia by immersing participants in the challenges faced by dyslexic students. These results align with previous research demonstrating that VR can enhance empathy for individuals with disabilities [41]. Compared to traditional awareness methods such as text-based or video interventions, the interactive and embodied nature of VR provides a more engaging and impressive experience [42].

Beyond its practical contributions, the study supports key theoretical frameworks. The results align with embodied cognition theory, which suggests that active engagement enhances learning and understanding [43]. Situating these findings within the broader research landscape, this study contributes to the emerging field of VR-based disability awareness [24,44]. While VR has been extensively explored for cognitive training, including in the dyslexia field [45], its application in fostering social awareness remains underdeveloped. The results presented suggest that VR can effectively complement existing educational interventions by providing an experiential understanding of dyslexia.

Despite its promising results, the study faced limitations. The sample size was relatively small, and it focused on higher education participants. Additionally, another important limitation of the proposal was that, despite the software being freely available to users, a Meta headset was required to participate in the experience. This requirement

represents a significant barrier, as the cost of such headsets may make them inaccessible to many potential users.

In summary, the study confirms that VR is a promising tool for dyslexia awareness, offering an immersive and engaging alternative to conventional methods. To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has explored the use of VR to foster empathy specifically for dyslexic individuals, making this work a novel contribution to the field. By situating the findings within prior research and theoretical frameworks, this work provides a foundation for future exploration of VR in inclusive education. The further refinement and expansion of these experiences will be essential to maximize their impact and accessibility.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

The findings of this study offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of the proposed VR experience in simulating the barriers encountered by dyslexic students and raising awareness about this SLD among participants. Overall, the tool demonstrated significant potential in achieving its awareness objectives, as reflected by a high average participant rating of 4.72 out of 5. This high level of satisfaction indicates that the VR experience effectively engaged participants and provided a meaningful understanding of the challenges associated with dyslexia.

As future work, and building upon the results of this initial evaluation, the next phase of research, currently in progress, focuses on the development and implementation of a structured set of activities to evaluate the effectiveness of VR as a tool for promoting empathy and raising awareness about dyslexia among undergraduate healthcare students. Among these activities, an adapted version of the Toronto Empathy Questionnaire (TEQ) [46] will be developed and contextualized for higher education students with dyslexia. This questionnaire will be administered both at the initial phase and post-intervention to check the impact of the experience.

The study will consist of three phases: baseline assessment, intervention, and follow-up evaluation. In the baseline phase, students' initial knowledge, empathy, and awareness of dyslexia will be assessed through pre-intervention surveys. During the intervention phase, third- and fourth-year healthcare students will participate in the VR-based program simulating the experiences of individuals with dyslexia. The participants will be randomly assigned to either an experimental group, which will engage with the VR intervention, or a control group, which will receive conventional educational instruction. The VR intervention comprises a 20-min immersive session illustrating the cognitive and emotional challenges associated with dyslexia. In the post-intervention phase, a follow-up survey will be conducted three weeks later [47] to evaluate changes in empathy and awareness. The customized TEQ outcomes will be compared between the experimental and control groups. The findings of this study aim to refine educational strategies in healthcare training, ultimately fostering greater empathy and a deeper understanding of learning disorders.

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